

Effect of *Narayana Taila Pratisarana* in *Dantaharsha* with special reference to Dentinal Hypersensitivity. A Clinical Case Study.

Dr. Shankar Laxmanrao Indurkar¹, Dr. Nisar Ali Khan²

¹M.S. (PG Scholar) 3rd Year, Department of Shalakyatantra, Government Ayurved College, Nanded.

²Professor, Shalakyatantra Department Government Ayurved College, Nanded.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shankar Laxmanrao Indurkar

ABSTRACT: *Acharya Sushruta* has described 65 *Mukha-Rogas*. *Dantaharsha* is one of them, commonly faced dental problem in dental OPDs. *Dantaharsha* is a condition where the teeth becomes intolerant to exposure of wind (*pravaata*), sour taste (*amla*), cold food items (*sheetha bhakshya*) and on intake of sour food items (*amlaashana*) there will be onset of short sharp pain (*saruja*). *Ayurveda Samhitas* and other *Ayurveda Granthas* have immense formulations (*yogas*) and treatment modalities like *Pratisarana Gandusha*, *Kavala* for the management of dental diseases. The line of treatment for *Dantaharsha* is mainly *Vatahara* treatment like *Narayana Taila Pratisarana*.

Materials and Methods

Male patient aged 25 years, who came to our *Shalakyatantra* Dental OPD, complaining of hypersensitivity of multiple teeth and gums of both upper and lower jaw along with pain for the past 2 months.

On examination the oral hygiene was found to be very poor and there was root exposure, attrition of gums, erosion, and abrasion in multiple teeth. Also considering the aggravating factors, *Dantaharsha* was diagnosed. For **Treatment** *Narayana taila pratisarana* was given for 14 days.

Result: The patient showed significant improvement in the assessment criteria.

KEYWORDS: *Dantaharsha*, Dentinal hypersensitivity, *Narayana Taila*, *Pratisarana*, Hydrodynamic theory.

INTRODUCTION

Acharya Sushruta has described the 65 *Mukha-Rogas*. Diseases of *Mukha Rogas* (oral cavity) are found to attack seven different locations viz, *Oshtha* (lips), *Dantamula* (gums), *Danta*(teeth), *Jivha* (tongue), *Talu*(palate), *Kantha*(throat) & *Sarvasara* (entire oral cavity). Teeth & Gums are important part of oral cavity [1].

According to *Ayurveda* there are eight *Dantagat rogas* i.e. *Dalan*, *Krimidant*, *Dantaharsha*, *Bhanjanaka*, *Sharkara*, *Kapalika*, *Shyavadanta*, *Hanumoksha* [2].

According to *Acharya Sushruta* patient is unable to bear cold and hot touch or only touch [3].

दशनाः शीतमुष्णं च सहन्ते स्पर्शनं न च ।

यस्य तं दन्तहर्षं तु व्याधि विद्यात् समीरणात् ।

According to *Acharya Vagbhata* cold air, sour food, cold food and sour substances are the cause of *Dantaharsha* [4].

Dantaharsha is described in classical *Ayurveda* as a condition where the teeth become incapable of tolerating breeze, eating sour and cold things, feels painful as though shaking. This produced by eating too much of sour things only.

“दन्तहर्षे दन्तेषु शीतोष्णादिभिः स्पर्शैः वेदना भवति।”

न चाश्नाति सुखं तेन दन्तहर्षः स उच्यते ॥^[5]

(अष्टाङ्गहृदयम्, उत्तरस्थानम्, 21/12)

This condition is understood as a *Vata*-dominant disorder involving *Shosha* (dryness) and *Srotodushti* (channel dysfunction)

Dantaharsha can be compared to Dentinal Hypersensitivity. When teeth are sensitized to cold/breeze hot dry and sour eatables and have pain and shaky feeling.

In modern dentistry, dentinal hypersensitivity is defined as short, sharp pain arising from exposed dentin due to enamel loss or gingival recession

The hydrodynamic theory explains pain due to fluid movement in dentinal tubules stimulating nerve endings in the pulp^[6].

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old male came to our *Shalakyatantra* Dental OPD, complaining of sharp dental pain of multiple teeth and gums of both upper and lower jaw due to cold, sweet, and brushing stimuli. He had also hyperacidity. Clinical diagnosis was Dentinal Hypersensitivity, and *Ayurvedic* diagnosis was *Dantaharsha*.

CONSENT: Implied consent taken.

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

The patient was apparently normal 3 months ago. Gradually he started experiencing acidity problems which he neglected. 2 months back the acidity problem aggravated followed by mild hypersensitivity in multiple teeth and gums of both upper and lower quadrants of oral cavity and he took modern medication which gave him temporary relief. After few days the hypersensitivity aggravated along with onset of pain in teeth. So, he came to our *Shalakyatantra* Dental OPD for management of his complaints.

HISTORY OF PAST ILLNESS: Nothing specific.

FAMILY HISTORY: Nothing specific.

Personal History:

Bowel: Mildly constipated

Appetite: Good

Sleep: Sound, 6-7 hours/night

Micturition: 5-6 times/ day

Habits / Addiction: no any

Tooth brushing: With hard bristle brush

No H/o any systemic illness

No H/o any Infective pathology

H/o Poor oral hygiene.

ASHTAVIDHA PAREEKSHAN

Nadi: 74/min

Mutra: 5-6 times/ day

Mala: Mildly constipated

Jihwa: *Lipta*

Shabda: *Prakrutha*

Sparsha: *Anushnasheeta*

Drik: *Spasta*

Aakruti: *Madhyama*

VITALS

Pulse rate: 74/min

Respiratory rate: 16/min

Temperature: 98.4⁰ F

B.P: 122/80 mmHg

AGGRAVATING FACTORS

Intake of cold food items Intake of hot, sour and spicy food items, Acidity.

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

Digestive System: Mildly constipated bowel Severe acidity

Other Systems: No abnormalities detected

SPECIFIC EXAMINATION:

DENTAL EXAMINATION

Oral hygiene: Poor

Dantamula (Gingiva)

Colour: pale

Contour: scapooled

Bleeding from gums: absent

Danta (Teeth) Number of teeth: 32

Colour: Yellowish white

Staining: Generalized brownish staining

Calculus: Generalized subgingival calculus

Mobility: No mobile teeth

Occlusion: No malocclusion

Food impaction: Present

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Objective Criteria

Pain on touch ✓ ✓ ✓

Subjective Criteria

Parameter Intensity of Dentine hypersensitivity (Before Treatment)

Intake of cold food items ✓ ✓ ✓

Intake of warm food items ✓ ✓ ✓

Intake of sour food items ✓ ✓ ✓

Touch

Along with the medication the following instructions were given Maintain good oral hygiene
Follow proper brushing techniques with soft bristles twice daily
Reduce excessive intake of hot, sour and spicy food items.

RESULT

After 21 days of treatment, both subjective as well as objective parameters showed significant improvement.

Intervention:

Narayana Taila Pratisarana

“नारायणतैलं वक्ष्ये वायुव्याधिविनाशनम्”^[7]

(*Bhaishajya Ratnavali – Vatavyadhi Adhikara*)^[8]

Procedure

1. Oral cavity cleaned by gargling with lukewarm water .
2. *Narayana Taila* applied over affected teeth with the help of finger tip and
3. Gentle rubbing (*Pratisarana*) for 5–10 minutes

RESULTS

SYMPTOMS	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
Sensitivity to sweet sour	+++	0
Sensitivity to hot	+++	0
Sensitivity to cold	+++	0
Touch Sensitivity	++++	0

DISCUSSION

Dantaharsha a *Vata* predominant condition mentioned in *Ayurveda Samhitas* is a common dental problem characterized by sharp shooting pain associated with intolerance of teeth to exposure of wind (*pravata*), sour taste (*amla*), cold food items (*sheetha bhakshya*) and on intake of sour food items (*amlaashana*). As mentioned in *Susrutha Samhita Uttaratantra Oupadravika Adhyaya*, the best treatment for any condition is *Nidana Parivarjana*. So, in this condition, the first step towards the management is avoidance of the aggravating factors like *Pravata*, *Amla*, and *Sheeta Bhakshana*.

The line of treatment for *Dantaharsha* is mainly *Vatahara* treatment. Use of *Vatahara* formulations for various *Ayurvedic* treatment modalities like *Pratisarana*, *Gandusha*, *Kavala* play vital role in the management of *Dantaharsha*.

CONCLUSION

Narayana Taila contains total 33 ingredients and all the ingredients are herbal. It is a unique *Taila Kalpana* that having wide range of treatment of diseases and extensively indicated in *Vata Pradhana Vyadhi*.

As per modern science Dentine hypersensitivity is a condition characterized by rapid, short, sharp pain arising from exposed dentin in response to the stimuli typically thermal, evaporative, tactile, osmotic, or chemical. Dentine hypersensitivity features are similar to *Dantaharsha*. Considering the special indication of *Narayana Taila Pratisarana* which gave significant result.

Mode Of Action

Probable *Ayurvedic* Action

1. *Vata shamana* (*Vata* pacification)

Narayana taila is *snigdha* and *ushna* so it opposes to *vata*.

In this way *vata shamana* is done .

2. *Snehana* (lubrication)

Tail penetrates in dental microchanelles (i.e,dentinal tubules)

3. *Brimhana* (tissue strengthening)

Due to *snigdha* property teeth are strengthened.

Modern:

This therapy forms protective lipid film coating enamel and dentin preventing direct stimulus and helps to regenerate decayed dentine.

Reduces fluid movement in tubules and decreases nerve excitation.

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